

A close look at young intermediate mass giant stars: clues of rotation and mixing

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In the search of a sample of metal-poor bright giant stars using Strömgren photometry, we serendipitously found a sample of 26 young (ages younger than 1 Gyr) metal-rich giants, with masses between 2.5 and 6 solar masses. Ten of these stars also rotate rapidly ($v \sin i > 10$ km/s). The high stellar masses imply that these stars were of spectral type A to B when on the main sequence. This evolutionary stage is not very well characterised by observations so far, because of the short time spent by stars in this phase. This sample of giant stars allows us a close look at this rapid evolution. It is an opportunity for testing the predictions of theoretical stellar tracks on the evolution of chemical abundances and rotational velocities.

Figure 1: Strömgren colour-magnitude diagram of the observed stars. Cyan lines represent Parsec isochrones with solar metallicity and ages between 0.1 and 1 Gyr, while grey lines represent Parsec isochrones with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.0$ dex and age 12 Gyr.

Target selection

The stars in our sample were selected by chance, as our initial intention was to select stars with a metallicity estimated by photometry in the range $-2.5 \leq [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -1.5$. For the target selection we used the Strömgren photometry from the Paunzen [1] catalogue and the metallicity calibration for giants of Casagrande et al. [2]. Our sample stars appeared to have a photometric metallicity in the metal-poor range, however, the analysis revealed that they are actually metal-rich, with metallicities around solar, and some of them are rotating rapidly. The reason for this discrepancy is essentially due to age-metallicity

degeneracy in the colour-magnitude diagram. Young isochrones with solar metallicity overlap with old metal-poor isochrones in the region of the colour-magnitude diagram where the stars in our sample are located (Figure 1). We suspect that the Casagrande et al. [2] calibration performs poorly on young metal-rich stars because these stars were not used to define the calibration. However we are not sure if the degeneracy could be broken, even if these calibrators were used, without introducing some age-sensitive quantity in the calibration.

Potentially binary stars

Two stars in our sample (HD 195375 and HD 278) are listed in the Washington Double Star Catalogue [3]. We checked the Gaia astrometric parameters of these two binary systems, and we found that HD 195375 and its companion have consistent parallaxes, so they are in a physical binary system, while HD 278 and its companion have different parallaxes, which implies that these stars are probably not in a binary system. We looked for other possible binary stars in our sample by comparing our measured radial velocities with those of Gaia Data Release 2 (DR2) [4]. In particular, we looked for stars with Gaia DR2 radial velocity that differs by more than 5σ from our measured velocity, and Gaia DR2 radial velocity errors above 1 km/s. Ten stars in our sample have also been identified as probable binary stars by Kervella et al. [5] by comparing HIPPARCOS [6] and Gaia DR2 proper motions. We found that two stars (HD 192045 and HD 213036) show all the above mentioned properties. This suggests that they are likely binary stars.

Figure 2: $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$ and $[\text{N}/\text{Fe}]$ abundance ratios as a function of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. Comparison with targets from Takeda et al. [7] (cyan crosses), and Royer et al. [8] (blue squares).

Chemical composition

We determined chemical abundances of 16 elements (C, N, O, Mg, Al, Ca, Fe, Sr, Y, Ba, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, and Eu) and rotational velocities of the stars using a set of high-resolution and high signal-to-noise spectra obtained with different spectrographs. The chemical analysis shows that all but two of the stars in the sample have low $[C/Fe]$ and high $[N/Fe]$ ratios (Figure 2). The $[(C+N+O)/Fe]$ ratio for these stars is almost constant and close to the solar value within the error bars. This pattern suggests that the material in the photosphere of the sample stars with sub-solar $[C/Fe]$ has been mixed with material that has experienced nuclear hydrogen burning through the CNO cycle. This interpretation is supported by the super-solar $[N/Fe]$ ratios and the constant $[(C+N+O)/Fe]$ ratio. The stars do not show any chemical peculiarities, except for the Ba abundance. The majority of the stars in the sample show a Ba abundance higher than solar, but solar neutron capture (n-capture) elemental abundances (Figure 3). The NLTE corrections for Ba lines are not sufficient to match the observed Ba abundances with the other n-capture abundances.

Figure 3: $[Ba/Fe]$ abundance ratios as a function of $[Fe/H]$. Comparison with targets from Bensby et al. [9] (grey crosses) and Royer et al. [8] (blue squares).

Because of the high Ba abundances, the stars in our sample might be Ba stars. According to de Castro et al. [10], the lower limit for Ba stars is $[s/Fe]=0.25$ dex, where $[s/Fe]=[Y/Fe]+[La/Fe]+[Ce/Fe]+[Nd/Fe]$. Only three stars in our sample have $[s/Fe]>0.25$, and only one star has $[s/Fe]=0.38$ (see Figure 4). These values are compatible with those of mild Ba stars. On the other hand, the other stars have $[s/Fe]$ values compatible with those of normal stars. In conclusion, the high $[Ba/Fe]$ ratios are puzzling and unexplained.

Figure 4: Mean $[s/Fe]$ abundance ratios as a function of $[Fe/H]$. Red circles represent $[s/Fe]$ ratio for the stars analysed in this work. Green squares represent Ba stars analysed in de Castro et al. [10]. Black squares represent the targets rejected as Ba stars in de Castro et al. [10].

Comparison with stellar evolution models

We measured the rotational velocities ($v \sin i$) of our sample stars and compared the results with theoretical models with rotation. We found a good agreement between the observed and predicted quantities. The $v \sin i$ we obtained for stars with $3.5 < M/M_{\odot} < 4$ and $-0.1 < [Fe/H] < 0.1$ ($5 < v \sin i < 22$ km/s) are compatible with the values of rotational velocity predicted by the Georgy et al. [11] models with $0.3 < \omega < 0.6$ ($\omega = \Omega_{in}/\Omega_{crit}$) at solar metallicity for stars in the corresponding region of the log T_{eff} versus log g diagram. We also found that the $[N/C]$ abundance ratios of our stars are compatible with the values predicted by rotational models for clump stars (the clump, or blue loop, is the region of the color-magnitude diagram where stars are located when they undergo central He-burning).

References

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